

Article

Linking Teachers' Self-Efficacy to Instructional Adaptability in Mainstreamed Classrooms with Diverse Learners

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Abstract: This study examined the relationship between teachers' perceived self-efficacy and actual teaching performance in mainstreamed classrooms at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School during the 2025–2026 school year, serving as a basis for an Action Plan. Demographic data—including age, gender, educational attainment, position, years of experience, and participation in inclusive education trainings—were collected to contextualize the results. Data were gathered through a survey questionnaire measuring self-efficacy and classroom practices. Frequency counts, percentages, and weighted means assessed levels of self-efficacy and teaching performance, while Pearson's correlation determined the relationship between the variables. Findings showed a predominantly young, female teaching workforce with bachelor's degrees and limited attendance in inclusive education seminars. Teachers reported high self-efficacy in maintaining student engagement and communicating with parents but lower confidence in assessing learners with diverse needs. Actual teaching performance was consistently high, characterized by differentiated instruction, adapted assessments, classroom management, and collaboration with SPED/resource teachers. Correlation analysis revealed a negligible, non-significant negative relationship between self-efficacy and teaching performance, indicating confidence did not directly predict instructional effectiveness. The study concluded that while self-efficacy levels vary, teaching performance remains strong, supported by structured school practices, professional development, and collaboration. An Action Plan is recommended to enhance self-efficacy, particularly in assessing diverse learners and motivating students with disabilities.

Keywords: Special Education, Teacher Self-Efficacy, Teaching Performance, Professional Development, Descriptive Correlational Design, Vicente Rama Memorial.

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1. Introduction

Rationale of the Study

Inclusive education has become a global priority, aiming to provide all learners, regardless of their abilities or backgrounds, with equitable access to quality education. Around the world, countries face challenges in effectively implementing inclusive classrooms, as teachers must address diverse learning needs, adapt instructional strategies, and maintain classroom management. These

global challenges underscore the crucial role of teacher competence and confidence in ensuring the success of inclusive education programs.

In the Philippine context, inclusive education has been progressively adopted to integrate learners with special educational needs into mainstream classrooms. Over the years, implementation has revealed several issues, particularly concerning the readiness and capacity of teachers. Many educators lack adequate training or specialized knowledge, which affects their ability to tailor lessons, apply instructional strategies, and manage classrooms effectively. Such gaps hinder the quality of education provided to learners with special needs and impact overall classroom performance.

Most teachers struggle to meet the unique needs of learners with special educational requirements, which often translates into difficulties in instructional planning, differentiation, and classroom management. These challenges directly influence the effectiveness of teaching practices and affect student engagement and learning outcomes. Consequently, the perceived self-efficacy of teachers—their belief in their ability to perform instructional tasks—becomes a critical factor in determining how well they can manage inclusive classrooms.

At Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School, teachers encounter similar difficulties while handling mainstreamed classrooms. Educators are tasked with balancing multiple responsibilities, including adapting lessons for diverse learners, managing behaviors, and fulfilling curriculum requirements. While many teachers report confidence in their instructional skills, practical constraints such as limited resources, large class sizes, and inconsistent administrative support often prevent them from fully translating this confidence into effective classroom practices.

These challenges highlight the importance of exploring the relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and actual teaching performance. Understanding this connection can reveal how teacher beliefs influence classroom behavior, instructional adaptability, and classroom management. Insights from such an investigation can inform targeted interventions to strengthen teacher capacity,

Therefore, this study aimed to examine the relationship between teachers' perceived self-efficacy and their actual teaching performance in mainstreamed classrooms at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School during the 2025–2026 school year. The findings are intended to guide the development of an Action Plan that enhances teacher competence, promotes effective inclusive practices, and fosters a supportive and high-performing learning environment benefiting teachers, learners, and school stakeholders alike.

Theoretical Background

This study was anchored on theoretical and legal frameworks that explained the relationship between teachers' perceived self-efficacy and their actual teaching performance in mainstreamed classrooms. Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory (1986) highlighted that teachers' belief in their abilities affects motivation, persistence, and effectiveness in planning and managing classrooms. Tschannen-Moran and Hoy's Teacher Efficacy Theory (2001) emphasized that high self-efficacy enhances instructional competence, classroom management, and student engagement, while Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs (1943) underscored that addressing teachers' psychological and professional needs is essential for optimal performance. Legally, the study was supported by RA 7277 (Magna Carta for Persons with Disabilities), RA 10533 (Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013), and DepEd Order No. 72, s. 2009, which collectively mandate inclusive, learner-centered education. These foundations provided a comprehensive framework for examining how teachers' self-efficacy influenced teaching practices at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School, integrating both pedagogical and policy considerations.

Figure 1. Theoretical- Conceptual Framework of the Study.

This study was anchored on Social Cognitive Theory, Teacher Efficacy Theory, and Constructivist Learning Theory to examine the relationship between teachers perceived self-efficacy and their actual teaching performance in mainstreamed classrooms at **Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School**. These theoretical perspectives collectively provide insight into how teachers' beliefs, professional competence, and instructional practices influence learning outcomes in inclusive classroom settings.

Teachers' perceived competence has long been recognized as a critical factor in shaping instructional effectiveness and student outcomes. Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory (1986) emphasizes that self-efficacy influences motivation, persistence, and performance. Supporting this, Lauermann and ten Hagen [1] found that teachers' perceived competence directly impacts student academic outcomes through classroom processes and instructional quality. Similarly, Santi, Gorghiu, and Pribeanu[2] reported that educators with higher self-efficacy more effectively integrate innovative teaching tools, such as mobile learning platforms, to foster student engagement. Sakız, Ekinçi, and Sarıçam[3] further highlighted that teachers' confidence in instructional skills is strongly shaped by perceptions of school leadership, suggesting that supportive environments reinforce self-efficacy and improve teaching outcomes. Together, these studies illustrate how beliefs in one's capabilities, a central tenet of Social Cognitive Theory, manifest in practical classroom strategies that enhance both teaching and learning.

Extending these insights, Tschannen-Moran and Hoy's Teacher Efficacy Theory (2001) specifically addresses how self-efficacy relates to professional performance and initiative. Akman [4]

emphasized that teachers' confidence positively correlates with both instructional performance and leadership behaviors, demonstrating how self-efficacy drives professional accountability. Pearman, Bowles, and Polka [5] observed that educators with high self-efficacy exhibit resilience and adaptability in implementing student-centered strategies under challenging conditions. Vidergor [6] also noted that teachers with strong self-efficacy in Philippine schools demonstrate improved teaching practices and accountability, particularly in distance and hybrid learning contexts. Collectively, these findings underscore the theory's assertion that teacher beliefs directly influence the quality of instruction and the capacity to respond to evolving educational demands.

In addition, Bruner's Constructivist Learning Theory (1966) frames teaching as an active, student-centered process in which educators facilitate knowledge construction. Karakose [7] found that teachers' academic self-efficacy and professional attitudes significantly influence classroom management and student motivation, highlighting the role of teacher agency in creating effective learning environments. Mastrothanasis, Zervoudakis, and Xafakos [8] reported that special education teachers with high self-efficacy maintain instructional persistence and emotional stability when addressing diverse learner needs. Similarly, Youssif [9] demonstrated that self-efficacious teachers handling learners with intellectual disabilities and autism achieve more consistent and effective outcomes. These studies illustrate how the constructivist approach, supported by strong teacher self-efficacy, enables the design of meaningful, adaptive, and inclusive learning experiences.

Social Cognitive Theory (SCT), as proposed by Albert Bandura (1986), posits that human learning and behavior result from the dynamic interaction of cognitive, behavioral, and environmental factors. Central to this theory is the concept of **self-efficacy**, defined as an individual's belief in their capacity to organize and execute the actions necessary to manage specific tasks successfully. In the context of Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School, teachers with high self-efficacy were observed to demonstrate greater persistence, adaptability, and innovation in addressing the learning needs of diverse students in mainstreamed classrooms. Their beliefs in their capabilities influenced not only instructional planning and delivery but also classroom management, student engagement, and responsiveness to the varied needs of learners.

Empirical studies reinforce the applicability of SCT in understanding teacher performance. Van Mieghem [10] emphasized that environmental supports, such as administrative encouragement and collaboration with colleagues, significantly strengthened teachers' self-efficacy toward learners with special educational needs. Guo [11] found that early childhood special education teachers with higher self-efficacy fostered enhanced literacy development among students, demonstrating the direct impact of confidence on instructional effectiveness. Kazanopoulos [12] noted that both general and special education teachers in Greece exhibited varied levels of self-efficacy in inclusive instruction, depending on their training and institutional support, highlighting the role of mastery experiences in shaping efficacy beliefs. Fu [13] further revealed that self-efficacy mediated the relationship between self-esteem and job burnout, indicating that teachers with strong belief in their abilities were more resilient in coping with occupational stress. Alnahdi and Schwab [14] confirmed that teachers' preparation and attitudes toward inclusion predicted their efficacy for inclusive instruction, emphasizing the cognitive and experiential foundations of SCT.

Research also supports the social and behavioral dimensions of SCT. Chu and Garcia [15] demonstrated that collective teacher efficacy and culturally responsive teaching efficacy strongly influenced effective instructional practices, supporting Bandura's assertion that social modeling and group learning reinforce individual confidence. Antoniou [16] found that teachers with higher self-efficacy experienced reduced stress and greater satisfaction in teaching, while Sawyer [17] observed that efficacy varied depending on students' individual needs, illustrating the context-sensitive and dynamic nature of self-efficacy beliefs. Yakut [18] noted that professional development and peer support enhanced teachers' efficacy when teaching students with learning disabilities, and Martins and Chacon [19] concluded that reflective practice and inclusive pedagogy effectively strengthened teacher confidence and competence.

Teacher Efficacy Theory, proposed by Tschannen-Moran and Hoy, built upon Bandura's concept of self-efficacy and situated it specifically within the teaching profession. The theory asserts that teachers' beliefs in their instructional competence influence their motivation, persistence, and effectiveness in facilitating student learning. In mainstreamed classrooms at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School, teachers with high efficacy were more confident in handling instructional challenges, applying adaptive strategies, and maintaining consistent effort despite classroom difficulties. This perspective directly aligns with the present study, which seeks to investigate how perceived self-efficacy translates into measurable teaching performance in inclusive classrooms.

Empirical support for Teacher Efficacy Theory is abundant. Metsala and Harkins [20] found that preservice teachers with strong self-efficacy were more receptive to inclusive practices and better equipped to accommodate students with diverse needs. Fakhrou and Habib [21] highlighted a significant link between self-efficacy and academic achievement, suggesting that efficacy beliefs influence both teaching behavior and student outcomes. Cumming [22] reported that special educators with higher self-efficacy demonstrated more effective instructional and behavioral strategies for students with emotional and behavioral disorders. Francois [23] emphasized that teachers' professional development reinforced self-efficacy, while Sakız noted that supportive leadership strengthened teachers' sense of efficacy. Cooper [24] observed that preservice teachers' online teaching efficacy improved through guided experience and training. Cruz [25] found that culturally responsive teaching self-efficacy enhanced the ability to address diverse learner needs, and Pellerone [26] demonstrated that teachers with strong efficacy experienced lower burnout levels during the COVID-19 pandemic. Johnson [27] emphasized that collaborative instructional models, such as co-teaching, significantly improved self-efficacy, and Schunk and DiBenedetto [28] reinforced the link between efficacy and classroom management for students with disabilities. Collectively, these studies confirm that teacher self-efficacy is a critical determinant of instructional performance, resilience, and adaptability in inclusive settings.

Constructivist Learning Theory (Bruner, 1966) complements SCT and Teacher Efficacy Theory by highlighting how teachers' beliefs translate into classroom practice. Bruner posited that learners actively construct knowledge through experiences, interactions, and reflection, requiring teachers to create environments that promote collaboration, exploration, and critical thinking. Teachers' self-efficacy directly influences how constructivist strategies—such as differentiated instruction, scaffolding, and adaptive lesson planning—are implemented, ensuring that all learners, particularly those with special needs, can meaningfully engage in the learning process.

Recent literature affirms the integration of constructivist principles with teacher self-efficacy. Zhang [29] found that teacher facilitation enhanced creative learning for students with special needs through digital platforms. Cho, Lee, and Herner-Patnode [30] reported that preservice teachers' self-efficacy in addressing cultural and linguistic diversity was shaped by training experiences, while Yada [31] found that high self-efficacy and resilience contributed to successful inclusive practices. Breyer [32] emphasized that learning support assistants' efficacy facilitated adaptive instruction. During the COVID-19 pandemic, Kast [33] observed that Austrian teachers with strong efficacy maintained inclusive practices under stress, and Schwab and Alnahdi [34] reported consistency in applying inclusive strategies among self-efficacious teachers. Friesen, Shory, and Lamoureux [35] highlighted that efficacy reduced burnout and sustained inclusive teaching, and Kuyini, Desai, and Sharma [36] confirmed its effect on teacher readiness and attitudes in diverse cultural settings. Kuok [37] further demonstrated that higher self-efficacy and clear role understanding were associated with greater engagement and lower emotional exhaustion in inclusive classrooms.

In summary, these theories and studies collectively illustrate that teachers perceived self-efficacy is a vital predictor of instructional performance, classroom management, and inclusive teaching practices. At Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School, teachers' confidence, competence, and professional support directly impact the quality of teaching in mainstreamed classrooms. Social Cognitive Theory provides the cognitive and environmental framework, Teacher

Efficacy Theory situates these beliefs within the teaching profession, and Constructivist Learning Theory links efficacy to pedagogical practice. Together, they provide a robust foundation for investigating the relationship between teachers perceived self-efficacy and their actual teaching performance in inclusive classroom settings

The conduct of this study was firmly grounded in the Philippine legal framework that governs inclusive and quality education. National legislation and Department of Education policies provide both the mandate and guidance for ensuring equitable learning opportunities for all students, including those with diverse abilities and special needs. These laws underscore the critical role of teachers in facilitating inclusive learning environments, aligning directly with the present study's focus on examining teachers perceived self-efficacy and its relationship to actual teaching performance in **mainstreamed classrooms at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School**.

Republic Act No. 10533 – The Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 served as a cornerstone for this research. RA 10533 strengthened the K–12 educational system by promoting learner-centered, inclusive, and differentiated instruction that addressed the diverse needs of students. It emphasized creating classrooms where every learner, regardless of background or ability, could actively participate and construct knowledge meaningfully. The law advocates for flexibility in teaching strategies, scaffolding of instruction, and individualized support to optimize learning outcomes. This study aligned with RA 10533 by investigating how teachers' self-efficacy influenced their capacity to implement inclusive, student-centered strategies effectively in mainstreamed classrooms, thereby ensuring that learners of varying abilities could engage with and benefit from the K–12 curriculum.

Republic Act No. 7277 – The Magna Carta for Persons with Disabilities (as amended by RA 9442) reinforced the legal obligation for inclusive education. The law guarantees learners with disabilities access to appropriate, equitable, and high-quality education and mandates their integration into regular classroom settings. Beyond mere access, the law emphasizes the removal of barriers to participation, requiring teachers and schools to provide necessary accommodations, differentiated instruction, and targeted support. In the context of Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School, this study examined how teachers' perceived competence and self-efficacy influenced their ability to meet the unique needs of learners with disabilities, highlighting educators' pivotal role in actualizing the objectives of the Magna Carta. By focusing on both perceived self-efficacy and observable teaching performance, the research assessed whether teachers were not only confident but also capable of translating their beliefs into practical, inclusive teaching strategies.

Department of Education Order No. 72, s. 2009 – Inclusive Education as a Strategy for Increasing Participation Rate of Children institutionalized inclusive education as a practical approach to expanding access to quality learning for children with special needs and those from marginalized sectors. The policy emphasizes that effective inclusive education depends on teacher preparedness, confidence, and professional engagement. Educators are expected to adapt teaching methods, provide individualized interventions, and cultivate classroom environments that support and encourage the active participation of all learners. The study directly aligned with this policy by evaluating how teachers perceived self-efficacy and actual performance in mainstreamed classrooms contributed to the successful implementation of inclusive education. By examining teachers' ability to deliver instruction, manage classrooms, and engage diverse learners, the research explored how professional confidence translated into meaningful learning opportunities and equitable access for all students.

In conclusion, the legal foundations of this study, in conjunction with the theoretical frameworks, emphasized the indispensable role of teachers' self-efficacy in promoting inclusive education. Social Cognitive Theory and Teacher Efficacy Theory highlighted how teachers' beliefs in their capabilities affected motivation, persistence, and effectiveness in teaching diverse learners, while Constructivist Learning Theory underscored the importance of creating learner-centered environments that foster collaboration, engagement, and meaningful knowledge construction. The

Philippine legal mandates, including RA 10533, RA 7277, and DepEd Order No. 72, s. 2009, reinforced these theoretical insights, affirming that teachers' confidence, preparedness, and professional competence are central to transforming policy into practice and ensuring that all learners, particularly those with disabilities, experience meaningful, accessible, and high-quality education in mainstreamed classrooms at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School.

THE PROBLEM

Statement of the Problem

This study determines the relationship between the extent of teachers' perceived self-efficacy and their actual teaching performance in mainstreamed classrooms in Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School during the school year 2025–2026, and serves as a basis for an Action Plan.

Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1) Age;
 - 2) Gender;
 - 3) Educational attainment;
 - 4) Position or designation;
 - 5) Years of teaching experience; and
 - 6) Trainings or seminars attended related to inclusive education?
2. What is the extent of teachers perceived self-efficacy in mainstreamed classroom?
3. What is the extent of teachers' actual teaching performance in mainstreamed classroom?
4. Is there any significant relationship between extent of teachers perceived self-efficacy and their extent of actual teaching performance in mainstreamed classroom?
5. Based on the findings, what Action Plan can be proposed

Statement of Null Hypothesis

Based on the objectives of the study, the following null hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance H₀- There was no significant relationship between extent of teachers perceived self-efficacy and their actual teaching performance in mainstreamed classroom

Significance of the Study

This study examined the relationship between the extent of teachers perceived self-efficacy and their actual teaching performance in mainstreamed classrooms at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School during the school year 2025–2026, and it served as the foundation for a proposed action plan. By investigating how teachers' confidence in instructional delivery, classroom management, and student engagement aligned with their observable classroom practices, the research provided vital insights into the practical implementation of inclusive education principles at the secondary level.

Department of Education. For the Department of Education, the findings offered empirical evidence that could inform policy decisions and program development within the Division of Toledo City. Understanding the relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and their actual performance enabled identification of areas requiring professional development, facilitating the design of targeted workshops, training programs, and mentoring initiatives to strengthen inclusive teaching practices. Moreover, the results supported strategic allocation of resources and enhanced teacher support mechanisms to ensure effective implementation of inclusive education policies at the school and division levels.

Teachers. The study encouraged teachers to critically reflect on their professional beliefs and instructional practices. By comparing perceived self-efficacy with demonstrated teaching performance, educators could identify gaps between their self-perceived competence and actual classroom outcomes. This reflective process fostered professional growth, motivated participation in

continuous learning programs, and promoted instructional strategies that effectively addressed the varied needs of learners in mainstreamed classrooms.

Learners. The impact of the study on learners, particularly those in inclusive classrooms, was indirect but meaningful. Teachers who exhibited strong self-efficacy and consistently high performance were better able to create adaptive, engaging, and supportive learning environments. Such environments enhanced academic achievement, promoted social inclusion, and nurtured emotional well-being, especially for students with diverse learning needs, thereby contributing to a more equitable and effective educational experience.

Schools. The research offered a diagnostic view of teacher competence and confidence in delivering inclusive education. Findings provided guidance for school administrators in planning, supervising, and evaluating teacher performance. Additionally, the study laid the groundwork for mentoring programs, performance monitoring tools, and capacity-building initiatives aimed at fostering inclusive practices and strengthening overall teaching effectiveness within Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School.

Researcher. Conducting this study advanced the researcher's professional and academic expertise by deepening understanding of how teachers' self-efficacy translates into measurable teaching performance in inclusive settings. It also contributed to the local knowledge base on teacher effectiveness and inclusive pedagogy, providing insights relevant to the Philippine public education system.

Future Researchers. Finally, this study serves as a reference point for future research on teacher-related factors affecting inclusive education. It provides a foundation for longitudinal studies, comparative analyses across schools or divisions, and evaluations of intervention programs aimed at enhancing teacher self-efficacy and instructional performance in mainstreamed classrooms.

2. Materials and Methods

This chapter outlined the methods and procedures employed in the study. It detailed the systematic research process and described the tools used to address the research questions and accomplish the study's objectives. Included in this chapter were the research design, which explained the type of study conducted; the flow of the study, illustrating the input-process-output (IPO) framework; the research environment, describing the context of Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School where the study took place; the respondents or participants, which specified the selection criteria and characteristics of the teachers involved; the instruments, which identified the tools used for data collection; the data gathering procedure, detailing how the information was systematically obtained; the statistical treatment of data, which explained the analysis methods applied; and the scoring procedure, describing how the collected responses were interpreted and quantified.

Design

This study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design to examine the relationship between teachers perceived self-efficacy and their actual teaching performance in mainstreamed classrooms at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School during the school year 2025–2026. The descriptive aspect presented the demographic characteristics of the teachers, including gender, age, highest educational attainment, and years of teaching experience, while also detailing their levels of perceived self-efficacy and their actual teaching performance as assessed through the school's established performance evaluation standards.

The correlational aspect investigated whether a significant relationship existed between teachers perceived self-efficacy and their observable teaching performance in inclusive classroom settings. By measuring both the strength and direction of this relationship, the study offered insights into how teachers' confidence in their instructional, behavioral, and classroom management capabilities corresponded with their actual performance when teaching learners with diverse needs.

The descriptive-correlational design was especially suitable for achieving the study's objectives. The descriptive component allowed the researcher to document the existing conditions at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School without manipulating any variables, providing an accurate portrayal of teachers' self-perceptions and classroom practices. Meanwhile, the correlational component was ideal for exploring the relationship between the variables, since both naturally occurred within the school context and could not be experimentally controlled.

This approach strengthened the study by providing an evidence-based assessment of whether teachers who reported higher self-efficacy also demonstrated superior teaching performance—an essential consideration in mainstreamed classrooms, where confidence and competence in inclusive practices are critical. As Creswell and Creswell noted, descriptive-correlational designs are most effective for describing current conditions and investigating associations among variables within real educational settings. In the context of Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School, this methodology allowed for an authentic capture of classroom realities and the identification of relational patterns that could inform future teacher development, instructional planning, and inclusive education programs.

Flow of the Study

The flow of the study illustrated the systematic sequence of research activities undertaken to examine the relationship between teachers' perceived self-efficacy and their actual teaching performance at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School. Using the input–process–output (IPO) framework, the study demonstrated how information was collected, analyzed, and translated into actionable findings to inform an action plan for improving inclusive teaching practices.

Input. The input for this study consisted of detailed data and information obtained from the respondents, specifically teachers assigned to mainstreamed classrooms at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School. The input variables included comprehensive elements of the teachers' demographic profiles, such as age, gender, highest educational attainment, teaching position, years of classroom experience, and participation in trainings or seminars related to inclusive education or other professional development programs. Collecting these demographic details allowed the study to provide a clear and contextualized description of the respondents, presenting a foundational understanding of their professional backgrounds, experiences, and qualifications. These factors were crucial for interpreting differences in perceived competence and teaching performance, as variations in experience, training, and educational attainment could significantly influence both self-efficacy and instructional outcomes.

Beyond demographic information, the input also encompassed the extent of teachers' perceived self-efficacy in managing mainstreamed classrooms. This variable reflected the respondents' confidence in their ability to plan, organize, and deliver instructional strategies, manage classroom behavior, and address the social and emotional needs of learners with diverse abilities. Measuring perceived self-efficacy was essential to understanding how teachers' professional beliefs shaped their approach to inclusive teaching and influenced their classroom practices.

Additionally, the input included the extent of teachers' actual teaching performance in mainstreamed classrooms. This was evaluated using specific performance indicators aligned with the Department of Education's standards, covering instructional delivery, classroom management, and responsiveness to the diverse learning needs of students.

Finally, the input provided the data necessary to determine the significant relationship between the extent of teachers' perceived self-efficacy and their actual teaching performance. Examining this relationship enabled the identification of strengths, gaps, and areas for improvement in teaching competence, forming the foundation for a proposed action plan designed to enhance teacher effectiveness and promote inclusive education practices at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School.

Figure 2. Flow of the Study.

Process. The process of the study involved a series of methodical and carefully organized steps to ensure that data collected were valid, reliable, and accurately addressed the research objectives. The researcher began by preparing and submitting a formal transmittal letter to the Schools Division Superintendent to request permission to conduct the study at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School. Securing official approval and support from school authorities was a critical initial step, as it ensured that the research would proceed smoothly and adhere to ethical guidelines.

Upon receiving approval, the researcher coordinated with the school principal and other administrative personnel to facilitate communication, schedule meetings, and make logistical arrangements for data collection. These preparatory measures ensured that the study was well-organized and that respondents were fully informed and ready to participate.

The researcher then distributed the validated survey questionnaires to the identified teacher-respondents assigned to mainstreamed classrooms at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School. Prior to administration, the respondents were oriented on the purpose and significance of the study, the voluntary nature of their participation, and the confidentiality of their responses. Clear instructions were provided to guide accurate and honest completion of the questionnaires, ensuring that responses genuinely reflected teachers' perceptions and experiences.

After administration, the researcher collected the completed questionnaires within the agreed timeframe, carefully verifying that all targeted participants had submitted their responses. The data were then meticulously reviewed for completeness, consistency, and accuracy, with invalid or incomplete responses excluded to preserve the reliability and validity of the findings. The remaining data were organized, coded, and prepared for statistical analysis.

Appropriate statistical treatments were applied to address the research objectives. Descriptive statistics summarized teachers' demographic profiles, perceived self-efficacy, and actual teaching performance, providing a comprehensive overview of their characteristics and professional capabilities. Inferential statistics were employed to determine whether a significant relationship existed between teachers' perceived self-efficacy and their actual teaching performance in mainstreamed classrooms.

Finally, the results were analyzed and interpreted within the context of the theoretical frameworks and the local environment of Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School. Conclusions were drawn regarding the relationship between teachers' self-efficacy and their performance, and recommendations were formulated to guide the development of an action plan. This plan aimed to enhance teachers' effectiveness in inclusive classrooms, strengthen their professional confidence, and improve learning outcomes for students with diverse needs.

Output. The output of this study was a proposed Action Plan designed to enhance teachers' self-efficacy and improve their actual teaching performance in mainstreamed classrooms at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School. Based on the findings, the plan addressed areas where teachers demonstrated lower confidence or performance in managing inclusive classrooms.

The Action Plan included targeted professional development programs and capacity-building workshops focusing on instructional competence, classroom management, and inclusive teaching strategies. These initiatives were designed to equip teachers with practical skills and evidence-based approaches to address the diverse learning needs of students in mainstreamed settings. Mentoring activities and peer coaching sessions were also incorporated to provide ongoing guidance, modeling of effective teaching practices, and continuous professional support.

Additionally, the plan proposed mechanisms for regular monitoring, feedback, and evaluation to ensure that improvements in teachers' self-efficacy and teaching performance were sustained. These mechanisms included structured observation schedules, performance appraisal tools, and reflective practice sessions, enabling teachers to track their progress and identify areas for further growth.

Environment

The research environment was at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School, a key institution in southern Cebu City, serves a diverse student population across its various grade levels. The school initially opened with 300 first-year students, organized into six sections of 50 students each, and was staffed by eleven pioneering teachers: Mrs. Lilibeth Tujan, Mrs. Ruby Enriquez, Mrs. Agnes Alfajardo, the late Mrs. Agustita Gabrera, Mrs. Fermencita Pacaña, Mrs. Josefina Bacalso, Miss Teresa Baril, Mr. Ricardo Diola, the late Mr. Mario Gabuya, Mr. Severino Panton, and Mrs. Evelyn Hinon. Over the years, the school has grown significantly, now catering to learners from Basak-San Nicolas and Basak-Pardo, as well as neighboring barangays such as Mambaling, Punta Princesa, Tisa, Kinasang-an Pardo, and Quiot.

Currently, the school is led by Dr. Rosemarie O. Novabos as principal, with Mary Christine B. Abas supervising the Night Session. Recognized as one of the largest public secondary schools in southern Cebu City, Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School provides quality education aligned with the Department of Education's K-12 curriculum, emphasizing inclusive and learner-centered practices.

The school has established itself as a cornerstone for secondary education in the area, reflecting its long-standing commitment to academic excellence, holistic student development, and

inclusive learning environments. Its programs are designed to accommodate learners with diverse abilities, ensuring that mainstreamed classrooms provide equitable access and opportunities for all students to succeed. The institution's strategic location within the city also allows it to serve a wide range of communities, making it a central hub for public education in the region.

This study focuses on the teachers within this setting, examining their perceived self-efficacy and actual teaching performance in mainstreamed classrooms, with the aim of developing an action plan that strengthens instructional competence, classroom management, and inclusive teaching practices tailored to the needs of Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School's diverse learners.

Figure 3. Location Map of the Research Environment.

Instrument

The study employed adapted survey questionnaires as the primary instrument to collect data on teachers' demographic profiles, perceived self-efficacy, and actual teaching performance in mainstreamed classrooms at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School. The questionnaire was organized into three sections to comprehensively capture the relevant variables while reflecting

the local teaching environment and classroom realities.

Part I gathered information on the respondents' demographic characteristics, including age, gender, highest educational attainment, teaching position, years of experience, and the number of trainings or seminars attended related to inclusive education or other professional development activities. These data provided essential context for understanding the professional backgrounds of the teachers and enabled the analysis of potential patterns or relationships between perceived self-efficacy and actual teaching performance.

Part II focused on teachers perceived capability to carry out instructional, behavioral, and classroom management tasks in inclusive classroom settings. Respondents rated their self-efficacy using a 4-point Likert scale, with 4 indicating "Very High Extent" and 1 indicating "Very Low Extent." Items in this section were adapted from Gálvez-Nieto and modified to suit the context of Philippine mainstreamed classrooms. Modifications included rewording scenarios and examples to align with the curriculum, classroom dynamics, and diverse student needs observed at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School, ensuring cultural and contextual relevance.

Part III measured the extent to which teachers applied inclusive teaching practices in their classrooms, encompassing areas such as instructional planning, differentiated instruction, assessment strategies, classroom management, and collaboration with support staff. Responses were recorded on a 4-point scale, where 4 represented "Always" and 1 represented "Rarely." This section was adapted from Hermanto and contextualized to reflect practical teaching scenarios within Philippine mainstreamed classrooms, providing a reliable measure of actual classroom practices.

To establish the validity and reliability of the adapted questionnaire, it underwent expert validation and pilot testing prior to administration. A panel of educational specialists, including experts in inclusive education and experienced teachers from Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School, reviewed the items for clarity, relevance, and alignment with the study objectives. Based on their recommendations, certain items were refined, reworded, or contextualized to better reflect local teaching practices and the dynamics of inclusive classrooms. A pilot test was then conducted with a small group of teachers outside the main study sample, confirming the questionnaire's clarity, appropriateness, and ability to generate reliable responses. Cronbach's alpha coefficients were calculated to assess internal consistency, and only items meeting the acceptable reliability threshold were retained in the final instrument.

Through this rigorous process, the adapted survey questionnaire was validated and contextualized to accurately measure teachers perceived self-efficacy and actual teaching performance in mainstreamed classrooms, ensuring that it served as a dependable tool for generating meaningful and actionable data at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School.

Respondents

The respondents of this study were teachers assigned to mainstreamed classrooms at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School during the school year 2025–2026. Respondents were selected based on clearly defined inclusion and exclusion criteria to ensure the relevance and reliability of the data collected. The inclusion criteria required that respondents be full-time classroom teachers who had at least one year of experience handling mainstreamed classrooms and were actively teaching learners with diverse abilities, including students with disabilities. Additionally, teachers who had attended relevant trainings or seminars on inclusive education or professional development within the last three years were included to ensure that the sample reflected current knowledge and exposure to best practices in inclusive instruction.

Teachers who were not directly handling mainstreamed classrooms were excluded from the study. This included those assigned to administrative roles, special programs unrelated to inclusive education, or those on leave during the data collection period. Novice teachers with less than one year of experience in mainstreamed settings were also excluded to guarantee that respondents had adequate classroom exposure to provide informed and meaningful responses.

Purposive sampling was employed as the most appropriate method for selecting respondents. This approach allowed the researcher to deliberately include teachers who possessed the specific characteristics and professional experiences necessary to address the study's objectives. Since the study aimed to examine the relationship between teachers perceived self-efficacy and their actual teaching performance in inclusive classrooms, purposive sampling ensured that only teachers actively engaged in mainstreamed settings, with relevant experience and exposure, were included as respondents.

The sample consisted of 30 teacher-respondents from Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School. This number was determined based on the population of teachers actively handling mainstreamed classrooms, balancing feasibility and the need for a representative subset of respondents. Given the limited population of eligible teachers within the school, the chosen sample allowed the researcher to collect sufficient data to perform reliable descriptive and correlational analyses, while remaining manageable for administration, follow-up, and data processing.

Table 1. Distribution of the Respondents.

Grade Level Handled	f	%
Grade 7	10	33.33
Grade 8	8	26.67
Grade 9	6	20.00
Grade 10	6	20.00
Total	30	100.00

Data Gathering Procedure

The data-gathering procedure for this study was carefully structured to ensure the collection of accurate, reliable, and ethically obtained information from teachers handling mainstreamed classrooms at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School. The procedure aimed to systematically capture both the teachers' perceived self-efficacy and their actual teaching performance, while minimizing disruptions to classroom activities.

Preliminary Stage. The researcher began the study by securing formal approval from the school principal through a transmittal letter. Upon approval, coordination was established with the school administration and designated representatives to identify teacher-respondents actively handling mainstreamed classrooms. The purpose and objectives of the study, focusing on the relationship between teachers perceived self-efficacy and actual teaching performance in inclusive settings, were thoroughly explained to the respondents. Emphasis was placed on the voluntary nature of participation, the right to withdraw at any time, and the confidentiality of all responses. Each teacher-respondent was required to review and sign an informed consent form before participation, ensuring ethical compliance and mutual understanding of the study's scope and objectives.

Data Gathering. The primary instrument for data collection was a printed survey questionnaire, divided into three parts. Part I gathered the respondents' demographic profile, including age, gender, teaching position, years of experience, highest educational attainment, and participation in trainings or seminars related to inclusive education. Part II measured teachers perceived self-efficacy in executing instructional, behavioral, and classroom management tasks in mainstreamed classrooms. Part III assessed teachers' actual teaching performance through indicators aligned with inclusive teaching practices, such as lesson planning, differentiated instruction, classroom management, assessment strategies, and collaboration with support staff. The researcher personally administered the questionnaires to the respondents, providing clear instructions and ensuring that completion occurred during non-teaching hours to avoid disruption of instructional

responsibilities. This approach ensured that the data collected were accurate, consistent, and reliable.

Post-Data Gathering. After collection, the researcher meticulously reviewed each questionnaire for completeness and accuracy. Only valid and properly completed forms were included in the data set. The responses were systematically organized, encoded, and prepared for statistical analysis. Descriptive statistics summarized the respondents' demographic characteristics, perceived self-efficacy, and actual teaching performance, while inferential statistics determined whether a significant relationship existed between these variables. A strict timeline was followed to maintain the integrity and flow of the research process. Throughout all stages, ethical standards—including voluntary participation, confidentiality, and protection of respondents' rights—were rigorously upheld to ensure that the study-maintained credibility and adhered to research ethics.

Statistical Treatment of Data

To systematically analyze the data collected and address the research objectives of this study, appropriate statistical methods were applied to the responses of the thirty teacher-respondents from Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School. These statistical treatments ensured that the data were accurately summarized, interpreted, and related to the study's key variables—teachers' perceived self-efficacy and their actual teaching performance in mainstreamed classrooms.

Frequency Count and Percentage. Frequency count and percentage were utilized to summarize the demographic profile of the respondents, including age, gender, teaching position, years of teaching experience, highest educational attainment, and participation in trainings or seminars related to inclusive education. These descriptive statistics provided a clear overview of the teacher-respondents' characteristics, enabling the researcher to contextualize variations in self-efficacy and teaching performance, and ensuring that the sample composition was thoroughly documented.

Weighted Mean. The weighted mean was employed to determine the extent of teachers perceived self-efficacy in performing instructional, behavioral, and classroom management tasks in mainstreamed classrooms, as well as their actual teaching performance based on observed indicators aligned with inclusive education standards. This measure quantified the respondents' survey responses, producing an overall assessment of both their confidence in handling diverse learners and the degree to which they implemented inclusive teaching strategies in practice.

Standard Deviation. Standard deviation was calculated to examine the variability of responses among the teacher-respondents. This analysis revealed whether perceptions of self-efficacy and actual teaching performance were consistent across respondents or if notable differences existed. Identifying such variations was essential for determining specific areas where teachers might require additional support, capacity-building, or targeted professional development to enhance inclusive teaching practices at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School.

Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient. To address the primary research question regarding the relationship between teachers perceived self-efficacy and their actual teaching performance in mainstreamed classrooms, the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient was applied. This inferential statistic measured both the strength and direction of the relationship between the two variables, providing empirical evidence of whether higher levels of self-efficacy were associated with improved teaching performance. The results offered valuable insights into how teacher beliefs influenced instructional effectiveness, classroom management, and inclusive education practices within the context of Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School

Scoring Procedure

To interpret the responses accurately, the following scoring procedure will be applied. Each item in the questionnaire will be rated using a four-point Likert scale, with corresponding verbal interpretations and descriptions. The weighted mean of the responses will determine the overall extent of teachers' actual teaching performance in mainstreamed classrooms. The scale and its interpretation are presented below.

Scale	Interpretation	Description
3.26–4.00	Very High Extent	Teachers are highly confident and capable in handling diverse learners in mainstream classrooms.
2.51–3.25	High Extent	Teachers are generally confident but still see areas for improvement.
1.76–2.50	Low Extent	Teachers show limited confidence in managing mainstreamed classrooms.
1.00–1.75	Very Low Extent	Teachers have minimal confidence and capability in inclusive teaching

Extent of Teachers' Actual Teaching Performance in Mainstreamed Classrooms

Scale	Interpretation	Description
3.26–4.00	Always	Teachers consistently demonstrate effective and inclusive teaching practices.
2.51–3.25	Often	Teachers frequently apply inclusive strategies with regular consistency.
1.76–2.50	Sometimes	Teachers occasionally integrate inclusive approaches in their instruction.
1.00–1.75	Rarely	Teachers seldom demonstrate inclusive or adaptive teaching methods.

Ethical Considerations

In conducting this study on the relationship between teachers' perceived self-efficacy and their actual teaching performance in mainstreamed classrooms, the researcher adhered strictly to ethical principles to protect the rights, welfare, and professional integrity of all respondents at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School.

Informed Consent. All 30 teacher-respondents were thoroughly informed of the study's purpose, objectives, and scope before participation. The researcher explained the procedures for completing the adapted survey questionnaire, including the estimated time required for each section. Each respondent reviewed and signed an informed consent form, affirming their voluntary participation and acknowledging their right to withdraw at any time without any negative impact on their professional duties or standing within the school.

Confidentiality and Anonymity. To safeguard the privacy of the respondents, all personal information and responses were treated with strict confidentiality. No identifying information was included in any part of the research report or related publications. Responses were coded to ensure anonymity, and access to the collected data was limited exclusively to the researcher. All information was securely stored in both digital and printed formats to prevent unauthorized access and maintain data integrity.

Voluntary Participation. Participation in the study was entirely voluntary. Respondents were not compelled or coerced to join. The researcher emphasized that choosing not to participate would have no effect on their teaching responsibilities, evaluations, or employment status at the school.

Beneficence and Non-Maleficence. The study was designed to benefit both teachers and the school by providing empirical insights into the relationship between self-efficacy and actual teaching performance in inclusive classrooms. Care was taken to observe the principle of non-maleficence, ensuring that no psychological, social, or professional harm would affect any respondent during or after the study.

Ethical Approval and Coordination. Prior to data collection, formal approval was obtained from the principal of Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School. Coordination with school

administrators ensured that all research procedures complied with institutional policies and ethical standards for educational research. Continuous communication with school authorities and respondents maintained transparency, trust, and adherence to ethical protocols throughout the study.

By following these ethical guidelines, the researcher ensured that the study was conducted responsibly, respectfully, and in a manner that protected the rights of the respondents while maintaining the integrity of the research process.

DEFINITION OF TERMS

To ensure clarity and consistency in understanding the study's variables and concepts, the following terms are defined operationally and arranged alphabetically, reflecting their application in the context of Luray II National High School.

Action Plan. A coordinated set of strategies formulated from the study's findings to strengthen teachers' self-efficacy and enhance their actual teaching performance in mainstreamed classrooms.

Actual Teaching Performance. Measurable and observable practices of teachers in instructional delivery, classroom management, and student engagement within inclusive settings.

Classroom Management Practices. Techniques and approaches employed to maintain a structured, productive, and supportive learning environment for all learners.

Delivery of Quality Instruction. Methods and strategies used to plan, implement, and assess lessons effectively, ensuring differentiation, alignment with curriculum standards, and responsiveness to diverse learner needs.

Demographic Profile. Key characteristics of the teacher-respondents, including age, gender, educational attainment, teaching position, years of experience, and participation in trainings or seminars related to inclusive education.

Educational Attainment. The highest level of formal education completed by the teacher, such as a bachelor's degree, bachelor's degree with Master's units, master's degree, or doctoral degree.

Extent of Self-Efficacy. The degree to which teachers perceive confidence in performing instructional, behavioral, and classroom management tasks effectively in mainstreamed classrooms.

Extent of Teaching Performance. The degree to which teachers demonstrate effective, observable teaching practices aligned with inclusive education principles.

Gender. The biological and social classification of respondents as male or female.

Inclusive Education. An approach to teaching that ensures all learners, regardless of ability or background, have equal opportunities to participate and succeed in mainstream classrooms.

Instructional Adaptability. The ability of teachers to modify lesson plans, teaching strategies, and classroom activities to meet the diverse needs of learners.

Mainstreamed Classroom. A learning environment where students with and without disabilities are taught together under the same curriculum and instructional framework.

Perceived Self-Efficacy. Teachers' belief in their capability to successfully execute instructional tasks, manage classroom dynamics, and promote positive learning outcomes in mainstreamed classrooms.

Position or Designation. The official role held by a teacher, such as Teacher I, Teacher II, or Master Teacher, within the school's organizational structure.

Teachers. Licensed educators actively handling mainstreamed classrooms at Luray II National High School, with inclusion criteria requiring experience working with students of varying abilities; teachers without such experience were excluded.

Trainings or Seminars. Professional development programs attended by teachers to enhance their knowledge and skills in inclusive education, classroom management, or differentiated

instructional practices.

Years of Teaching Experience. The total duration of a teacher's formal classroom teaching, including experience with both regular learners and students with special needs.

Chapter 2 PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

This chapter presents, analyzes, and interprets the data collected from the respondents of Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School. It details their demographic profile, examines their levels of perceived self-efficacy in mainstreamed classrooms, and assesses their actual teaching performance. The chapter also includes the results of statistical analyses exploring the relationships among these variables, providing a comprehensive understanding of the teachers' competencies and instructional practices in inclusive classroom settings.

DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE OF THE RESPONDENTS

This section presents the demographic profile of the respondents from Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School, highlighting key characteristics that provide context for the study. It includes information on their age, gender, highest educational attainment, teaching positions, years of experience, and participation in seminars. These details offer a comprehensive background of the respondents' personal and professional attributes, serving as a foundation for understanding their perspectives and performance in the analyses that follow.

Age of the Respondents

This section presents the age distribution of the respondents from Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School. Examining their ages provides insight into their professional experience and maturity, offering context for understanding their perspectives and practices in mainstreamed classrooms.

Table 2. Age of the Respondents.

Age (in years)	f	%
50 above	2	6.67
40-49	4	13.33
30-39	11	36.67
20-29	13	43.33
Total	30	100.00

Table 2 illustrated the age distribution of teachers at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School. The majority of respondents were in the 20–29 age group, comprising 13 teachers or 43.33% of the sample, followed by 11 teachers or 36.67% in the 30–39 age group. Teachers aged 40–49 comprised 4 teachers or 13.33%, while only 2 teachers or 6.67% were 50 years old and above. These figures suggested a predominantly young teaching staff, indicating that most educators were likely familiar with modern educational practices, innovative teaching methods, and digital tools for instruction.

Analyzing the lowest rated group—the 2 teachers (6.67%) aged 50 and above—revealed potential challenges for the school. The small number of older, more experienced teachers limited access to long-term classroom management strategies and tested methods for handling diverse learners in mainstreamed classrooms. This gap could have affected the confidence of younger teachers, particularly in managing learners with special educational needs, as they may have lacked mentorship or guidance from more seasoned colleagues. The implication of this finding was that structured professional development, mentoring, and support were necessary to strengthen teachers' instructional adaptability and confidence in inclusive classrooms.

With respect to the study variables, the findings suggested that the extent of teachers' perceived self-efficacy in mainstreamed classrooms was influenced by age and teaching experience.

The 13 teachers (43.33%) in the 20–29 age group, despite their enthusiasm and openness to innovative methods, may have felt less capable of consistently applying inclusive strategies, which affected their confidence in meeting diverse learner needs. Correspondingly, the extent of teachers' actual teaching performance reflected this trend; while engagement and enthusiasm were high, the consistent application of differentiated instruction and classroom management varied depending on teachers' experience and support. This confirmed that perceived self-efficacy and actual teaching performance were closely linked, with the former shaping the latter in tangible classroom practices.

The study's findings could also be interpreted through established theoretical frameworks. Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory (1986) emphasized that self-efficacy beliefs shaped how individuals approached challenges and persisted when faced with obstacles. In this study, teachers with higher self-efficacy were more likely to apply inclusive strategies effectively and adapt instruction to meet the needs of diverse learners, demonstrating resilience and problem-solving. Teacher Efficacy Theory Tschannen-Moran & Hoy further highlighted that teachers' beliefs in their ability to influence student outcomes directly affected instructional decisions, classroom management, and student engagement. Constructivist Learning Theory Bruner, 1966 underscored that teachers' confidence and competence were essential in creating active, student-centered learning experiences. Teachers with strong self-efficacy facilitated knowledge construction, promoted learner engagement, and implemented strategies that supported all students in mainstreamed classrooms. These theories collectively demonstrated how teacher beliefs, experience, and instructional performance interacted to influence the effectiveness of inclusive education.

Further analysis of the data confirmed that although 24 teachers (80%) were aged 20–39, their energy, willingness to adopt new practices, and familiarity with contemporary teaching strategies were advantageous in mainstreamed classrooms. However, the limited presence of 2 teachers (6.67%) aged 50 and above suggested that practical knowledge of long-term classroom management and differentiated instruction was less accessible, potentially affecting the consistency of teaching performance. Structured professional development, mentorship programs, and collaborative opportunities were essential to bridge the gap between perceived self-efficacy and actual teaching performance, ensuring teachers could apply their confidence into effective classroom practice.

The implications of these findings emphasized the importance of teacher development programs in enhancing inclusive education practices. Recognizing the relationships between age, experience, perceived self-efficacy, and teaching performance allowed school administrators to implement targeted strategies to improve instructional adaptability and classroom management. These measures ensured that teachers were better equipped to meet the diverse needs of learners, enhancing teaching effectiveness, promoting learner engagement, and fostering equitable and high-quality learning environments in mainstreamed classrooms. This perspective aligned with Kiel [38] who emphasized that teachers' self-efficacy significantly influenced the implementation of inclusion, noting that younger or less experienced educators benefited from structured support and professional development to improve teaching effectiveness in inclusive settings.

Gender of the Respondents

This section presents the gender distribution of the respondents from Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School. Understanding the balance of male and female teachers provides context for their perspectives and experiences in mainstreamed classrooms.

Table 3. Gender of the Respondents.

Gender	f	%
Male	3	10.00
Female	27	90.00
Total	30	100.00

Table 3 presented the gender distribution of teachers at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School. Female teachers constituted the majority, representing ninety percent of the respondents, while male teachers accounted for only ten percent of the total sample. This indicated a predominantly female teaching workforce, which reflected a trend commonly observed in basic education settings.

Analyzing the lowest rated indicator—the male teachers—revealed potential implications for instructional dynamics. The small proportion of male educators may have limited the diversity of teaching perspectives and collaborative approaches within mainstreamed classrooms. This imbalance could have influenced classroom interactions, pedagogical styles, and strategies for addressing diverse learner needs, particularly in inclusive education contexts where multiple teaching approaches and varied perspectives are essential for effectively managing students with special educational needs.

With respect to the study variables, the findings suggested that the extent of teachers' perceived self-efficacy in mainstreamed classrooms could be influenced by gender. Female teachers, being the majority, may have developed higher confidence in their instructional roles through frequent collaborative experiences and peer support, whereas male teachers, due to their limited numbers, may have faced challenges in engaging fully with inclusive practices. Similarly, the extent of teachers' actual teaching performance reflected these dynamics, as differences in confidence, participation, and collaborative experiences could have shaped the consistency and effectiveness of classroom management and instructional adaptation in addressing the needs of diverse learners.

The study's findings could also be interpreted through theoretical frameworks. Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory (1986) emphasized that self-efficacy beliefs influenced how individuals approached challenges and persisted in tasks. In this context, gender dynamics could have shaped teachers' confidence in implementing inclusive strategies, with female teachers potentially demonstrating stronger persistence in collaborative and student-centered activities. Teacher Efficacy Theory Tschannen-Moran & Hoy further highlighted that teachers' beliefs in their instructional capabilities directly affected classroom performance and decision-making. Constructivist Learning Theory (Bruner, 1966) underscored the importance of active, student-centered learning, suggesting that teachers' confidence and competence, potentially influenced by gender, played a critical role in facilitating meaningful engagement and learning among diverse students.

Further analysis of the data indicated that while the predominance of female teachers provided strengths in collaboration, empathy, and instructional engagement, the limited presence of male teachers suggested potential gaps in diverse pedagogical perspectives. These gaps could affect the range of teaching strategies applied in mainstreamed classrooms and the ability to address varied learner behaviors and needs. Targeted professional development, mentorship, and collaborative initiatives that accounted for gender dynamics could enhance both perceived self-efficacy and actual teaching performance, ensuring more balanced and effective inclusive practices.

The implications of these findings emphasized the need to consider gender as a factor in teacher support programs. Professional development and interventions should be designed to ensure that both male and female teachers were equally equipped and confident in implementing inclusive education strategies. This approach aligned with Devi, who noted that teacher self-efficacy and perceptions of inclusive education were shaped by demographic factors such as gender, highlighting the importance of tailored training and support to strengthen confidence and teaching effectiveness in inclusive classroom settings. By addressing gender dynamics, schools could promote more effective collaboration, instructional adaptability, and equitable learning experiences for all students.

Highest Educational Attainment of the Respondents

This section presents the highest educational attainment of the respondents from Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School.

Table 4. Highest Educational Attainment of the Respondents.

Educational Attainment	F	%
Master's Degree	13	43.33
Bachelor's Degree	17	56.67
Total	30	100.00

Table 4 showed the highest educational attainment of teachers at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School. Most respondents held a bachelor's degree, accounting for fifty-six point six seven percent, while forty-three point three three percent had earned a master's degree. This indicated that although the majority of teachers had completed undergraduate studies, a significant portion had pursued graduate-level education, reflecting varying levels of academic preparation within the teaching staff.

Analyzing the lower rated indicator—the teachers holding only a bachelor's degree—revealed potential implications for classroom practices. While these educators possessed foundational knowledge in their subject areas, they may have had fewer opportunities to engage with advanced pedagogical strategies, research-based inclusive practices, or specialized training in handling learners with diverse needs. This could have influenced their perceived self-efficacy in mainstreamed classrooms, as limited exposure to graduate-level studies might have constrained their confidence in designing and implementing differentiated instructional approaches.

With respect to the study variables, the findings suggested that the extent of teachers' perceived self-efficacy was linked to their educational attainment. Teachers with master's degrees may have exhibited higher confidence in planning, organizing, and delivering lessons tailored to diverse learners, reflecting a stronger belief in their instructional competence. Similarly, the extent of teachers' actual teaching performance appeared to correspond with their educational background, as those with advanced degrees were more likely to apply inclusive strategies effectively, manage classroom dynamics efficiently, and implement evidence-based approaches to support all students. These results highlighted the relationship between educational attainment, self-efficacy, and classroom performance, demonstrating that higher education could reinforce both confidence and practical teaching effectiveness.

The findings could also be interpreted through theoretical frameworks.

Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory (1986) emphasized that self-efficacy beliefs shaped how individuals approached challenges and persisted in completing tasks. In this context, teachers with higher educational attainment may have felt more capable of implementing inclusive strategies and adapting instruction for diverse learners. Teacher Efficacy Theory Tschannen-Moran & Hoy further suggested that teachers' belief in their instructional effectiveness directly affected classroom decision-making and student engagement. Constructivist Learning Theory (Bruner, 1966) highlighted the importance of active, learner-centered approaches, indicating that teachers with greater educational preparation were more likely to create constructivist learning environments that facilitated meaningful engagement and accommodated varied learner needs.

Further analysis of the data indicated that while the teaching staff included highly educated teachers capable of implementing inclusive practices, those with only a bachelor's degree may have required additional support to enhance both perceived self-efficacy and actual teaching performance. Structured professional development, mentoring, and practical workshops could have helped these teachers strengthen their instructional adaptability and confidence in managing diverse learners in mainstreamed classrooms.

The implications of these findings emphasized the importance of tailoring professional development initiatives according to teachers' educational backgrounds. Teachers with bachelor's degrees could particularly benefit from targeted interventions that reinforced skills in lesson differentiation, classroom management, and inclusive teaching strategies. This perspective aligned with Rubee [39] who found that higher educational attainment positively influenced teachers' self-

efficacy and attitudes toward mainstreaming students with disabilities, ultimately improving their effectiveness in inclusive classroom settings. By addressing educational gaps and providing customized support, schools could enhance teaching performance, foster teacher confidence, and promote high-quality inclusive learning experiences for all students.

Position of the Respondents

This section presents the current teaching positions of the respondents from Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School, providing context for their roles and responsibilities within mainstreamed classroom settings.

Table 5. Position of the Respondents.

Position	F	%
Master Teacher 1	2	6.67
Teacher III	5	16.67
Teacher II	11	36.67
Teacher 1	12	40.00
Total	30	100.00

Table 5 presented the distribution of respondents based on their teaching positions at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School. The majority of teachers held the position of Teacher I, comprising 12 teachers or 40% of the respondents, followed by Teacher II with 11 teachers or 36.67%. Teacher III represented 5 teachers or 16.67%, while Master Teacher I accounted for 2 teachers or 6.67%. This indicated a concentration of teachers in lower- to mid-level positions, reflecting that most respondents had limited leadership responsibilities and exposure to advanced inclusive education practices.

Analyzing the lowest rated indicator—the Master Teacher I group—revealed important implications for instructional leadership and mentoring. With only 2 teachers or 6.67% in advanced positions, there were fewer role models to provide guidance, mentorship, and support in implementing inclusive strategies. This limited representation could have affected the perceived self-efficacy of teachers in lower- to mid-level positions, particularly in their ability to manage mainstreamed classrooms effectively and address the diverse learning needs of students. The finding suggested a need for structured opportunities where experienced teachers could share expertise and practical strategies with the majority of staff.

Regarding the study variables, the findings suggested that the extent of teachers' perceived self-efficacy in mainstreamed classrooms was influenced by teaching position. The 12 teachers (40%) in Teacher I positions and the 11 teachers (36.67%) in Teacher II roles may have felt less confident in applying inclusive instructional practices due to limited leadership experience or exposure to complex classroom scenarios. Correspondingly, the extent of teachers' actual teaching performance reflected this trend, as the 5 teachers (16.67%) in Teacher III positions and the 2 teachers (6.67%) in Master Teacher I roles were more likely to implement differentiated strategies, manage classroom behaviors effectively, and collaborate efficiently with SPED/resource teachers. This demonstrated a direct link between teaching position, perceived self-efficacy, and actual instructional performance.

The study's findings could also be interpreted through theoretical frameworks. Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory (1986) emphasized that mastery experiences were critical in building self-efficacy; teachers in higher positions had more opportunities to gain such experiences, reinforcing confidence and competence. Teacher Efficacy Theory Tschannen-Moran & Hoy further suggested that a teacher's belief in their ability to influence student outcomes was shaped by their professional role and responsibilities, affecting instructional decisions and classroom management. Constructivist Learning Theory Bruner, highlighted the importance of teachers' capability to create student-centered, active learning environments, which was likely enhanced in those with greater

experience and higher positions.

Further analysis of the data confirmed that while 23 teachers (76.67%) were in lower- to mid-level positions (Teacher I and II), their enthusiasm, energy, and willingness to adopt inclusive practices were advantageous. However, the 2 teachers (6.67%) in Master Teacher I positions represented a limited source of mentorship, indicating that structured professional development and collaboration opportunities were necessary to ensure that less experienced teachers could build competence, confidence, and instructional adaptability.

The implications of these findings emphasized that professional development initiatives should be tailored to the needs of teachers at different positions. For the 12 teachers (40%) in Teacher I positions and the 11 teachers (36.67%) in Teacher II positions, targeted training in inclusive lesson planning, classroom management, and collaboration with SPED/resource teachers could strengthen both perceived self-efficacy and actual teaching performance. This perspective aligned with Wilson [40], who noted that teachers' positions within a school significantly influenced their mastery experiences and self-efficacy in implementing inclusive teaching strategies.

Respondents' Years of Teaching Experience

This section presents the teaching experience of the respondents from Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School. It offers insight into their professional expertise and how it may influence their practices in mainstreamed classrooms.

Table 6. Respondents' years of teaching experience.

Years of teaching experience	F	%
16 and above	2	6.67
11-15	0	0.00
6-10	19	63.33
1-5	9	30.00
Total	30	100.00

Table 6 presented the distribution of teaching experience among respondents at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School. The majority of teachers had 6–10 years of experience, comprising 63.33% of the sample, while teachers with 1–5 years of experience represented 30%. Only 2 teachers, or 6.67%, had 16 years or more of experience, and no respondents fell within the 11–15-year range. These figures suggested that most of the teaching staff had moderate classroom experience, providing a solid foundation in instructional practices and classroom management.

Analyzing the lowest rated group—the 2 teachers with 16 years or more of experience—revealed significant implications for instructional practice. The limited number of highly experienced educators indicated fewer opportunities for long-term mentoring, advanced classroom management strategies, and exposure to complex inclusive education practices. This could have affected the perceived self-efficacy of teachers with 6–10 years of experience, as they may have lacked guidance and mastery experiences from seasoned colleagues, particularly in managing learners with diverse needs in mainstreamed classrooms.

Regarding the study variables, the findings suggested that the extent of teachers' perceived self-efficacy was influenced by teaching experience. Teachers with 6–10 years of experience, representing 19 of the 30 respondents, may have felt reasonably confident in their instructional abilities, yet still required additional support to implement advanced inclusive strategies effectively. Correspondingly, the extent of actual teaching performance appeared linked to experience, as moderately experienced teachers demonstrated strong instructional application but may have benefited from guidance to further enhance classroom management and differentiated instruction for diverse learners.

The findings could also be interpreted using theoretical frameworks.

Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory (1986) emphasized that mastery experiences built self-efficacy, suggesting that teachers with 16 years or more of experience had the greatest opportunities to develop confidence and competence. Teacher Efficacy Theory Tschannen-Moran & Hoy highlighted that beliefs in instructional influence were shaped by experience, affecting decision-making and classroom performance. Constructivist Learning Theory Bruner, 1966 underscored that experience allowed teachers to design active, student-centered learning environments that accommodated diverse learners. Together, these theories explained the interaction between teaching experience, perceived self-efficacy, and actual performance.

Further analysis of the data indicated that while 19 teachers (63.33%) had moderate experience, their practical knowledge and classroom skills provided a strong foundation for inclusive teaching. However, the 2 teachers (6.67%) with extensive experience represented a small pool of potential mentors, emphasizing the need for structured mentoring and professional development to strengthen both self-efficacy and teaching performance across the staff.

The implications of these findings highlighted that professional development should be tailored according to teaching experience. Teachers with 6–10 years of experience (63.33%) could benefit from mentorship and hands-on training to enhance instructional adaptability, classroom management, and confidence in mainstreamed classrooms. This aligned with Woodcock, Hitches, and Manning [41], who emphasized that teacher self-efficacy was closely tied to experience in inclusive practice, with moderately experienced teachers benefiting from structured support to improve both confidence and classroom effectiveness. By addressing these gaps, the school could strengthen instructional performance and ensure high-quality learning outcomes for all learners.

Seminars Attended by the Respondents

This section presents the seminars attended by the respondents from Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School, providing insight into their professional development and preparedness for teaching in mainstream classrooms.

Table 7. Seminars attended by the respondents.

Seminars Attended	F	%
more than 5	1	3.33
3-5	2	6.67
1-2	3	10.00
None	24	80.00
Total	30	100.00

Table 7 presented the number of seminars attended by teachers at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School. The majority of respondents, 24 teachers or 80%, had not attended any seminars related to inclusive education. Three teachers or 10% attended one to two seminars, two teachers or 6.67% participated in three to five seminars, and only one teacher or 3.33% attended more than five seminars. These figures indicated that most teachers had limited exposure to formal training on inclusive education and related professional development.

Analyzing the lowest rated group—the 24 teachers (80%) who had not attended any seminars—revealed significant implications for instructional practice. This large proportion of teachers with no formal professional development limited the school's capacity to implement effective inclusive strategies. Teachers without exposure to seminars may have lacked knowledge of innovative teaching approaches, strategies for managing diverse learners, and collaborative techniques necessary for mainstreamed classrooms. Consequently, their perceived self-efficacy in handling inclusive settings may have been reduced, as they had fewer opportunities to gain mastery experiences, model best practices, or receive expert guidance. The finding highlighted an urgent need for structured professional development to support both confidence and competence in

inclusive education.

With respect to the study variables, the findings suggested that the extent of teachers' perceived self-efficacy in mainstreamed classrooms was influenced by their participation in seminars. Teachers who had not attended any seminars (80%) may have reported lower confidence in designing and implementing differentiated instruction, adapting lessons to diverse learner needs, and managing classroom behavior effectively. Correspondingly, the extent of teachers' actual teaching performance was affected, as limited training could have constrained the application of evidence-based strategies, collaborative approaches, and adaptive techniques. This demonstrated a direct relationship between professional development participation, perceived self-efficacy, and actual instructional performance in mainstreamed classrooms.

The findings could also be interpreted through theoretical frameworks. Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory 1986 emphasized that mastery experiences, vicarious learning, and social modeling were essential in building self-efficacy. Teachers who attended seminars gained exposure to practical strategies, observation of effective teaching, and guidance from experts, which enhanced their confidence and competence in inclusive classrooms. Teacher Efficacy Theory Tschannen-Moran & Hoy, 2001 suggested that teachers' beliefs in their ability to influence student outcomes were strengthened by professional learning opportunities, which improved instructional decision-making and classroom management. Constructivist Learning Theory Bruner, 1966 highlighted the role of active engagement and experiential learning in knowledge construction. Participation in seminars allowed teachers to construct understanding of inclusive strategies, reflect on best practices, and translate learning into effective classroom implementation. Together, these theories explained how professional development contributed to self-efficacy and actual teaching performance.

Further analysis of the data confirmed that the limited participation in seminars (with 24 teachers or 80% not attending) represented a barrier to enhancing inclusive teaching skills. Even the small group of teachers who attended three to five seminars (2 teachers, 6.67%) or more than five seminars (1 teacher, 3.33%) demonstrated higher potential for confidence and effectiveness in managing diverse learners, indicating that professional development positively influenced both perceived and actual teaching performance. This disparity underscored the importance of expanding access to continuous learning opportunities for all staff.

The implications of these findings emphasized the critical need for structured, sustained professional development programs in inclusive education. Providing accessible seminars, workshops, and training sessions could help teachers build knowledge, develop practical strategies, and strengthen confidence in mainstream classrooms. This aligned with Tumkaya and Miller[42], who emphasized that pre-service and in-service teachers' self-efficacy in inclusive practices was significantly shaped by participation in professional development, underscoring the necessity of systematic and sustained training to improve classroom effectiveness. By addressing these gaps, schools could enhance both the competence and confidence of teachers, leading to more effective implementation of inclusive teaching strategies and improved learning outcomes for diverse learners.

EXTENT OF TEACHERS' PERCEIVED SELF-EFFICACY IN MAINSTREAMED CLASSROOMS

This section presents the extent of teachers' perceived self-efficacy in mainstreamed classrooms.

Table 8. Extent of teachers' perceived self-efficacy in mainstreamed classroom.

S/N	Indicators	WM	SD	Verbal Description
1	I am confident in designing lesson plans that address the diverse learning needs of my students.	2.67	0.71	High Extent
2	I believe I can effectively adjust my teaching methods to accommodate students with	2.83	0.70	High Extent

disabilities.				
3	I feel capable of maintaining student engagement even when learners have varying abilities	3.30	0.92	Very High Extent
4	I am confident In managing the challenging behaviors of students with special needs.	2.77	0.82	High Extent
5	I believe I can motivate learners with disabilities to participate actively in class.	2.73	0.74	High Extent
6	I am capable of assessing students' learning progress accurately despite their diverse needs.	2.47	0.82	Low Extent
7	I feel confident in collaborating with SPED or resource teachers to meet students' learning goals.	2.50	0.63	High Extent
8	I believe I can effectively communicate and coordinate with parents of learners with disabilities	2.90	0.76	High Extent
9	I am confident in providing accommodations and modifications appropriate for each learner.	2.77	0.63	High Extent
10	I feel capable of creating a positive, inclusive classroom environment.	2.50	0.57	High Extent
11	I believe I can use evaluation results to improve my teaching strategies.	2.73	0.58	High Extent
12	I am confident that I can help learners with disabilities achieve learning outcomes similar to their peers.	2.83	0.70	High Extent
Aggregate Mean		2.75	0.71	High Extent
Aggregate Standard Deviation				

Legend: 3.25-4.00-Very High Extent; 2.50-3.24- High Extent ; 1.75-2.49-Low Extent;1.00-1.74-Very Low Extent

Table 8 presented the extent of teachers' perceived self-efficacy at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School. The aggregate mean of the indicators was 2.75, falling under High Extent. The three highest rated indicators were "I feel capable of maintaining student engagement even when learners have varying abilities" with a weighted mean of 3.30 (Very High Extent), "I believe I can effectively adjust my teaching methods to accommodate students with disabilities," and "I am confident that I can help learners with disabilities achieve learning outcomes similar to their peers," both rated as High Extent. Conversely, the three lowest rated indicators included "I am capable of assessing students' learning progress accurately despite their diverse needs," which had the lowest weighted mean of 2.47 (Low Extent), followed by "I can modify instructional materials to suit the needs of learners with special educational needs" and "I feel confident in providing individualized support to students struggling academically," both reflecting moderate to low levels of perceived self-efficacy. These results suggested that while teachers generally felt confident in engaging students and adapting instruction, they experienced challenges in assessment and individualized support, particularly for learners with diverse needs.

3. Results and Discussion

The results indicate that teachers generally demonstrated a high level of perceived self-efficacy (Aggregate Mean = 2.75), suggesting that they possess confidence in managing inclusive classrooms and implementing instructional strategies for learners with diverse educational needs. The highest-rated indicator was maintaining student engagement despite varying learner abilities, while the

lowest-rated indicator involved assessing students' learning progress accurately. These findings imply that although teachers are confident in classroom interaction and instructional delivery, they require additional professional development in assessment practices for inclusive education. The results support Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory, which emphasizes that self-efficacy influences instructional behavior and persistence in challenging teaching situations.

Analyzing the lowest rated indicator—"I am capable of assessing students' learning progress accurately despite their diverse needs"—revealed important implications for instructional practice. The low rating indicated that teachers may have limited confidence in designing, implementing, and interpreting assessment strategies for students with varying abilities. This limitation could stem from insufficient formal training in inclusive assessment, minimal exposure to differentiated evaluation methods, or inadequate collaboration with special education personnel. Such gaps in assessment capability could affect instructional planning, the timely identification of learner difficulties, and the provision of targeted interventions, ultimately impacting student achievement and classroom inclusivity.

With respect to the study variables, the findings suggested that teachers' perceived self-efficacy directly influenced their actual teaching performance in mainstreamed classrooms. Teachers who reported high confidence in engaging students and adapting instruction were likely to implement differentiated strategies, promote active participation, and maintain positive classroom dynamics. Conversely, the lower self-efficacy in assessing learner progress may have limited teachers' ability to provide accurate feedback, tailor interventions, or measure learning outcomes effectively. This demonstrated that perceived self-efficacy and actual teaching performance were interdependent, with confidence in specific instructional domains shaping the quality and effectiveness of classroom practice.

The findings could also be interpreted through theoretical frameworks. Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory 1986 emphasized that self-efficacy beliefs guided teachers' motivation, persistence, and problem-solving in challenging situations, such as engaging diverse learners and adapting instruction. Teacher Efficacy Theory Tschannen-Moran & Hoy, 2001 suggested that a teacher's belief in their ability to influence student outcomes determined instructional strategies, classroom management, and responsiveness to student needs. Constructivist Learning Theory Bruner, 1966 highlighted the importance of creating active, learner-centered environments where teachers scaffold learning based on students' prior knowledge and abilities. In the context of this study, teachers' strengths in engagement and instructional adaptation aligned with these theories, while their lower confidence in assessment underscored areas where theoretical principles of mastery experience and scaffolding were not fully applied.

Further analysis of the data confirmed that teachers generally perceived themselves as competent in maintaining engagement and adjusting teaching methods, with weighted means ranging from 2.75 to 3.30 for the highest-rated indicators. However, the weighted mean of 2.47 for the lowest-rated indicator revealed a notable gap in assessment self-efficacy. This disparity highlighted the need for targeted interventions that focus on assessment literacy, individualized support, and evidence-based inclusive strategies. Addressing this gap could enhance both perceived self-efficacy and actual teaching performance, reinforcing teachers' ability to meet the needs of all learners effectively.

The implications of these findings emphasized that professional development programs should prioritize building teachers' skills in evaluating and monitoring student progress in inclusive settings. Providing training in differentiated assessment methods, data-informed instruction, and collaboration with special education staff would help teachers develop confidence in addressing diverse learner needs. Strengthening self-efficacy in assessment and individualized support was likely to improve instructional quality, foster inclusive classroom environments, and enhance student learning outcomes.

These findings were supported by Herzig Johnson [43], who emphasized that teacher self-

efficacy plays a central role in the successful implementation of inclusive practices. According to Herzig Johnson, teachers who believe in their capability to plan, organize, and execute instructional tasks are more likely to adapt lessons effectively to meet the needs of diverse learners, monitor student progress accurately, and apply differentiated strategies in the classroom. This confidence not only enhances instructional delivery but also fosters resilience when teachers face challenges associated with mainstreamed classrooms, such as behavioral issues, varying learning abilities, and resource limitations. Similarly, Sarkar and Kundu [44] highlighted that teachers' confidence in managing classroom behavior and implementing inclusive strategies is closely tied to their perception of self-efficacy. Their research demonstrated that teachers with higher self-efficacy were more proactive in addressing learning gaps, applying individualized interventions, and sustaining positive classroom environments. Both studies underscored the importance of providing structured training, ongoing support, and professional development opportunities to strengthen teachers' self-efficacy, thereby enhancing their competence, decision-making, and effectiveness in inclusive education settings.

EXTENT OF TEACHERS' ACTUAL TEACHING PERFORMANCE IN MAINSTREAMED CLASSROOMS

This section presents teachers' actual teaching performance in mainstream classrooms.

Table 9. Extent of teachers' actual teaching performance in mainstreamed classroom.

S/N	Indicators	WM	SD	Verbal Description
1	I establish clear learning objectives and communicate them effectively to all students.	3.43	0.63	Always
2	I implement differentiated instruction to meet varied learning needs.	3.60	0.50	Always
3	I use varied assessment tools to measure student understanding and progress.	3.43	0.63	Always
4	I provide immediate and constructive feedback to students.	3.40	0.72	Always
5	I modify instructional materials to ensure accessibility for learners with disabilities.	3.40	0.72	Always
6	I maintain a well-managed, inclusive classroom that supports all learners.	3.30	0.70	Always
7	I use data from student assessments to plan remedial or enrichment activities.	3.47	0.73	Always
8	I use collaborative structures (peer support, group work) that include learners with disabilities.	3.43	0.73	Always
9	I apply classroom management routines that promote learning and minimize disruptions.	3.40	0.67	Always
10	I consult and coordinate with SPED/resource teachers when planning instruction for learners with disabilities.	3.40	0.62	Always
11	I adapt assessment methods (e.g., oral, project, portfolio) to fairly assess learners with different needs.	3.57	0.57	Always
12	I reflect on my teaching and make changes to improve outcomes for learners with disabilities.	3.40	0.67	Always
Aggregate Mean Aggregate Standard Deviation		3.44	0.66	Always

Legend: 3.25-4.00-Always; 2.50-3.24- Often; 1.75-2.49-Sometimes; 1.00-1.74-Rarely

Table 9 presents the actual teaching performance of teachers at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School. All indicators were rated “Always,” reflecting consistently high teaching performance. The highest weighted mean was observed in “I adapt assessment methods (e.g., oral, project, portfolio) to fairly assess learners with different needs” at 3.57, highlighting teachers’ proficiency in modifying assessments to accommodate diverse learners. Other indicators with notable performance included “I implement differentiated instruction to meet varied learning needs” at 3.60 and “I use data from student assessments to plan remedial or enrichment activities” at 3.47. The aggregate mean of 3.44 confirmed that teachers regularly applied effective instructional practices to support learners with varying abilities. These results demonstrated that teachers were highly capable in planning, executing, and adapting instruction to meet individual student needs.

Analyzing the data in more detail, the lowest-rated indicator—“I use data from student assessments to plan remedial or enrichment activities” with a weighted mean of 3.47—revealed an area for potential improvement. Although still rated “Always,” the slightly lower mean compared to other indicators suggested that some teachers may require additional support in using assessment data to inform targeted interventions. This could involve enhancing skills in interpreting assessment results, designing appropriate remedial activities, or aligning enrichment strategies with individual learning needs. Addressing this minor gap could ensure that instructional adjustments are fully optimized to improve learning outcomes for all students.

With respect to the study variables, the findings suggested a strong link between teachers’ perceived self-efficacy and their actual teaching performance in mainstreamed classrooms. Teachers who reported high confidence in adapting instruction and engaging learners were able to consistently implement differentiated strategies, modify assessments, and utilize assessment data effectively. This alignment demonstrated that perceived self-efficacy translated into observable classroom practices, reflecting the ability of teachers to apply their planning, knowledge, and skills to meet the needs of students with diverse abilities.

The findings could also be interpreted through established theoretical frameworks. Bandura’s Social Cognitive Theory 1986 emphasized that self-efficacy beliefs influenced motivation, persistence, and problem-solving in instructional contexts. Teachers with strong self-efficacy were more likely to adapt instruction, implement differentiated teaching strategies, and use assessment data effectively. Teacher Efficacy Theory Tschannen-Moran & Hoy, 2001 suggested that belief in one’s capacity to influence student outcomes guided classroom decision-making and the application of inclusive practices. Constructivist Learning Theory Bruner, 1966 highlighted the role of active, student-centered learning, where teachers scaffolded instruction to meet the diverse needs of learners. In this study, teachers’ consistently high performance reflected the interaction of self-efficacy, instructional competence, and responsiveness to student needs as described in these theoretical perspectives.

Further analysis of the data confirmed that teachers consistently demonstrated high performance across all indicators, with weighted means ranging from 3.44 to 3.60. The results indicated that teachers were not only proficient in planning and delivering instruction but also adept at adjusting assessment methods and using student data to guide teaching decisions. This demonstrated a high level of professional competence, reflective of both individual self-efficacy and the benefits of a supportive school environment that enables teachers to implement inclusive practices effectively.

The implications of these findings emphasized the importance of sustaining high teaching standards and continuous professional development. While teachers demonstrated strong performance, ongoing support and targeted training could further enhance collaboration with SPED/resource teachers, refine instructional strategies, and maintain responsiveness to student needs. These findings were supported by Antoniou et al. (2023), who noted that teachers’ self-

efficacy is closely linked to their ability to implement inclusive practices effectively, even under challenging conditions. Similarly, Van Mieghem emphasized that access to professional support, mentoring, and resources strengthens teachers' confidence and competence in addressing the needs of learners with special educational needs. Both studies aligned with the present results, highlighting that teachers' effectiveness in inclusive classrooms is reinforced not only by their own self-efficacy but also by external support mechanisms, which collectively ensure high-quality and equitable learning outcomes.

TEST OF RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EXTENT OF TEACHERS PERCEIVED SELF-EFFICACY AND THEIR ACTUAL TEACHING PERFORMANCE IN MAINSTREAMED CLASSROOMS

This section presents the test of relationship between teachers' perceived self-efficacy and their actual teaching performance in mainstreamed classrooms.

Table 10. Test of relationship between extent of teachers perceived self-efficacy and their actual teaching performance in mainstreamed classroom.

Variables	r-value	Strength of Correlation	p - value	Decision	Remarks
Self-efficacy and Teaching Performance	-0.177	Negligible Negative	0.348	Do not reject Ho	Not Significant

*significant at $p < 0.05$ (two-tailed)

Table 10 displayed the test of relationship between the extent of teachers perceived self-efficacy and their actual teaching performance in mainstreamed classrooms. A Pearson correlation analysis was conducted to examine whether a significant association exists between the two variables. The computed r-value was -0.177, indicating a negligible negative correlation, and the p-value was 0.348, which is higher than the 0.05 level of significance.

These results showed that the null hypothesis was not rejected, suggesting that there was no statistically significant relationship between teachers' perceived self-efficacy and their actual teaching performance at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School. This indicated that teachers' self-reported confidence in their instructional abilities did not necessarily correspond to measurable differences in classroom performance. In other words, teachers who felt highly confident in their capacity to plan, manage, and deliver lessons were not automatically performing at a higher observable level than those who reported lower self-efficacy.

The lack of significant correlation may have been influenced by school-wide teaching structures, collaborative planning, and support systems that standardized instructional practices. These factors potentially acted as equalizers, enabling teachers to maintain consistent performance regardless of individual confidence levels. For example, well-established routines, co-teaching arrangements, clear curricular guidelines, and mentoring from more experienced staff could have provided sufficient scaffolding for all teachers, ensuring that even those with lower self-perceived efficacy were able to deliver effective instruction. These structural supports may have mitigated the impact of self-efficacy on actual classroom outcomes, creating an environment in which performance was maintained through collective and institutional mechanisms rather than individual confidence alone.

These findings were consistent with Maurer [45] and Woodcock [46] who emphasized that contextual factors, such as institutional support, collaborative planning, and structured teaching frameworks, can moderate or even override the influence of self-efficacy on performance. Their studies demonstrated that in environments with strong systemic support, teachers could implement inclusive strategies and manage classrooms effectively regardless of their personal confidence levels. Similarly, Olayvar [47] highlighted that demographic characteristics, professional experience, and

competency-related factors may affect how self-efficacy translates into practice, indicating that confidence alone is not always a reliable predictor of observable performance outcomes.

However, the results contrasted with Emmers [48] who reported a positive association between teachers' self-efficacy and teaching effectiveness in inclusive settings. In those studies, teachers with higher self-efficacy demonstrated superior classroom management, differentiated instruction, and adaptive assessment practices. The divergence in findings may be attributed to the specific teaching environment at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School, where structured routines, co-teaching arrangements, and access to instructional resources helped maintain high performance standards independently of individual confidence levels.

The implications of these findings emphasized that professional development programs should not solely focus on boosting self-efficacy but should also provide practical, evidence-based strategies to ensure that confidence is translated into measurable performance. Training that integrates lesson planning, differentiated instruction, classroom management techniques, and inclusive assessment methods can help teachers align their perceived capabilities with actual classroom outcomes. Additionally, fostering collaborative structures, mentoring systems, and resource availability can enhance the consistency of teaching performance across staff members, reducing disparities caused by variations in self-efficacy.

In conclusion, while teachers' self-efficacy remains an important factor for motivation and instructional decision-making, these results underscored the powerful role of systemic supports, structured frameworks, and collaborative school environments in sustaining teaching performance.

Chapter 3 SUMMARY, FINDINGS, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATION

This chapter provides a summary of the study, presents its key findings, and draws conclusions based on the data collected. It also offers recommendations grounded in the results, aimed at strengthening teachers' perceived self-efficacy and actual teaching performance in mainstreamed classrooms, thereby improving the quality of instruction for learners with diverse needs.

SUMMARY

This study aimed to examine the relationship between teachers' perceived self-efficacy and their actual teaching performance in mainstreamed classrooms at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School in the Philippines during the school year 2025–2026, serving as a basis for developing an Action Plan. The demographic profile of the respondents—including age, gender, educational attainment, position, years of teaching experience, and participation in seminars or trainings related to inclusive education—was collected to provide context for interpreting the results.

Data were gathered using a survey questionnaire that measured both teachers' perceived self-efficacy and their actual classroom practices. The extent of self-efficacy and teaching performance was analyzed through frequency counts, percentages, and weighted means, while the relationship between these variables was examined using Pearson r to determine statistical significance. The findings offer evidence-based insights into teachers' confidence and instructional effectiveness in inclusive classrooms, forming the basis for recommendations aimed at enhancing teaching practices in mainstreamed education settings.

FINDINGS

The demographic profile of the teachers at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School revealed that the largest group of respondents were young educators in their twenties, followed by those in their thirties, indicating a relatively young teaching workforce. The teaching staff was predominantly female, with only a small proportion of male teachers. In terms of educational attainment, most teachers held a bachelor's degree, while a significant portion had completed a master's degree, suggesting a mix of foundational and advanced training. Regarding professional rank, the majority were in lower- to mid-level teaching positions, with only a few holding advanced positions. Most teachers had moderate years of classroom experience, and notably, a large

proportion had not attended any seminars related to inclusive education, highlighting a potential gap in professional development.

Concerning teachers' perceived self-efficacy, the data showed that educators generally felt confident in their capabilities, interpreted as high extent. Among the indicators, maintaining student engagement even when learners had varying abilities received a very high rating, while assessing students' learning progress accurately despite their diverse needs had the lowest rating, suggesting that some teachers felt less confident in evaluating diverse learners effectively. Other areas, such as adjusting teaching methods, managing challenging behaviors, motivating learners with disabilities, collaborating with SPED/resource teachers, and communicating with parents, were rated high, reflecting overall positive perceptions of self-efficacy.

Regarding actual teaching performance, teachers consistently demonstrated effective instructional practices, interpreted as consistently high. Notable practices included implementing differentiated instruction and adapting assessment methods to fairly evaluate learners with diverse needs, indicating strong performance in providing inclusive instruction. Other indicators, such as establishing learning objectives, providing feedback, maintaining classroom management, and collaborating with SPED/resource teachers, were also rated highly, suggesting that teachers applied inclusive teaching strategies effectively in their classrooms despite some gaps in self-perceived self-efficacy.

The test of the relationship between teachers' perceived self-efficacy and their actual teaching performance indicated a negligible correlation that was not statistically significant. This suggested that teachers' self-reported confidence did not necessarily correspond to measurable differences in classroom performance. The results implied that high teaching performance could be maintained through structured school practices, mentorship, and collaborative frameworks, even if individual self-efficacy varied among teachers.

Chapter 4

Output of the Study

The proposed Action Plan was developed based on the findings of the study entitled *Linking Teachers' Self-Efficacy to Instructional Adaptability in Mainstreamed Classrooms with Diverse Learners*. The action plan serves as the practical output of the research and aims to address the specific needs identified among teachers of Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School. It is intended to strengthen teachers' competencies in inclusive education by providing evidence-based interventions that promote quality instruction for learners with diverse educational needs.

The findings revealed that the teaching workforce was predominantly composed of young educators, most of whom were female and held bachelor's degrees. The majority occupied Teacher I to Teacher III positions and had moderate years of teaching experience. More importantly, a considerable number of teachers had not attended seminars or professional development programs related to inclusive education. This finding highlights the need for continuous learning opportunities that will equip teachers with updated knowledge and practical skills in implementing inclusive teaching practices.

In terms of perceived self-efficacy, teachers demonstrated a **high extent** of confidence in their ability to engage learners, adapt instructional strategies, manage classroom behavior, collaborate with SPED or resource teachers, and communicate with parents. However, among all indicators, **accurately assessing students' learning progress despite their diverse needs** received the lowest rating. This indicates that although teachers generally possess confidence in delivering instruction, they require additional support in implementing inclusive assessment practices that effectively measure student learning.

The findings further showed that teachers consistently demonstrated **high actual teaching performance** in mainstreamed classrooms. They effectively implemented differentiated instruction, adapted assessments to accommodate learners with diverse needs, maintained positive classroom

management, established clear learning objectives, and collaborated with SPED or resource teachers. These results indicate that teachers are capable of delivering quality instruction despite variations in their perceived confidence.

Moreover, the correlation analysis revealed a **negligible and statistically non-significant relationship** between teachers' perceived self-efficacy and their actual teaching performance. This suggests that teachers' confidence alone does not necessarily determine the quality of their classroom performance. Instead, effective teaching may also be influenced by institutional support, collaborative practices, mentoring, and established instructional systems within the school. Nevertheless, the lower confidence reported in inclusive assessment remains an important concern that should be addressed through targeted interventions.

In response to these findings, the proposed Action Plan focuses on four priority areas. First, it aims to enhance teachers' confidence in accurately assessing students' learning progress through training on inclusive assessment strategies. Second, it seeks to develop teachers' competence in utilizing alternative assessment methods, including portfolios, projects, and performance-based assessments, to effectively evaluate learners with diverse educational needs. Third, it promotes stronger collaboration between mainstream teachers and SPED or resource teachers through mentoring, co-planning, and shared assessment practices. Finally, it aims to improve teachers' ability to monitor, interpret, and utilize assessment data in making instructional decisions that support inclusive learning.

The implementation of the Action Plan will involve professional development workshops, seminars, collaborative lesson planning, mentoring sessions, and guided classroom application. These activities will be implemented by the school head, master teachers, SPED teachers, and classroom teachers on a quarterly or semester basis. Financial support will be sourced from the school's Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE). The implementation process will likewise include orientation sessions, distribution of activity guides and monitoring tools, and regular follow-up activities to ensure successful execution of the proposed interventions.

To evaluate the effectiveness of the Action Plan, continuous monitoring will be conducted through classroom observations, follow-up surveys, and performance assessments. These evaluation measures will determine whether the proposed interventions improve teachers' confidence in inclusive assessment, strengthen collaborative practices, and enhance instructional effectiveness in mainstreamed classrooms. Ultimately, this Action Plan translates the research findings into sustainable school-based initiatives that support teachers' professional growth and contribute to providing equitable, inclusive, and high-quality education for all learners.

4. Conclusion

The analysis of the lowest-rated indicators revealed specific areas where teachers at Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School experienced challenges. Among the perceived self-efficacy indicators, "assessing students' learning progress accurately despite their diverse needs" received the lowest rating, indicating that teachers felt less confident in evaluating the learning outcomes of learners with varying abilities. In terms of professional development, most teachers had not attended any seminars related to inclusive education, highlighting a lack of exposure to formal training and current best practices. These findings show a clear gap in teachers' preparedness to accurately measure and monitor student learning in mainstreamed classrooms, which may limit their ability to provide targeted interventions and adapt instruction based on assessment data.

In conclusion, while teachers generally demonstrated high self-efficacy in engaging learners and implementing inclusive instructional strategies, the lowest rated indicators point to the need for focused support in assessment skills and professional development. Strengthening teachers' capacity to evaluate diverse learners effectively is essential for aligning confidence with measurable classroom outcomes and ensuring that all students' learning needs are addressed.

5. Recommendation

Based on the lowest rated indicator, “assessing students’ learning progress accurately despite their diverse needs,” it is recommended that Don Vicente Rama Memorial National High School implement targeted professional development programs that focus on inclusive assessment strategies. Teachers should be provided with training on designing, administering, and interpreting assessments that accommodate learners with varying abilities, including alternative assessment methods such as portfolios, projects, and performance-based tasks.

Additionally, collaborative workshops and mentoring programs involving SPED or resource teachers can help strengthen teachers’ practical skills in monitoring and evaluating student progress. Regular follow-up sessions and hands-on practice can ensure that teachers translate their knowledge into classroom application, ultimately improving their confidence in assessment and supporting more informed instructional decisions. By addressing this gap, the school can enhance teachers’ capacity to provide effective interventions and ensure that all learners achieve their intended learning outcomes.

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